

On the SINR Meta Distribution of UAV-assisted Wireless Networks

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Outline

- Introduction
 - Stochastic geometry
 - SINR/SIR meta distribution
 - UAV communication
- SINR meta distribution of UAV-assisted networks
 - Downlink performance analysis
- Conclusion

Introduction

Stochastic Geometry

- Stochastic geometry is a strong mathematical tool based on probability theory that enables capturing the spatial randomness in wireless networks.
- Enables analyzing the statistical characteristics of various metrics such as SNR, SINR.
- The main advantage is the capability to derive tractable mathematical expressions for the performance metrics, which can be used to replace time-consuming simulations.
- Has been widely used over past decade to study large-scale wireless networks.

Introduction

Stochastic Geometry

- Take Poisson point process (PPP) for example:

The locations of points is modeled by a PPP, Φ , with density, λ .

The number of points in an area $A \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is Poisson distributed with mean $\lambda |A|$, and the points are uniformly distributed inside A .

Introduction

Stochastic Geometry

- Stationarity (HPPP)
- Distance distribution:

$$F_R(r) = \mathbb{P}(R < r) = 1 - \mathbb{P}(R > r) = 1 - \exp(-\lambda |A|) \mathbb{P}(\mathcal{N}(B(0,r)) = 0).$$

- Interferer characterize:

$$\mathbb{E}[I] = \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i \in \mathbb{N}} p_t h_i |x_i|^{-\alpha} \right] = p_t \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{i \in \mathbb{N}} |x_i|^{-\alpha} \right] = p_t 2\pi\lambda \int_1^{\infty} \frac{1}{r^{-\alpha}} r dr.$$

Introduction

SINR meta distribution

- Coverage probability: the typical user is successfully served, its SINR is above a predefined threshold,

$$P_{cov}(\theta) = \mathbb{P}(\text{SINR} > \theta),$$

- in which,

$$\text{SINR} = \frac{p_t h_{x_0} ||x_0||^{-\alpha}}{\sum_{x \in \Phi \setminus \{x_0\}} p_t h_x ||x||^{-\alpha} + \sigma^2},$$

- Fundamental of many other performance metrics: such as average achievable rate...

Introduction

SINR meta distribution

- Coverage probability is a spatial average performance, it provides limited information of an individual link.
- Two cellular networks have the same coverage probability but may totally different.
- What is the reliability and quality of service of networks?
- SINR meta distribution: defined as the complementary cumulative distribution function (CCDF) of conditional success probability:

$$\bar{F}(\theta, \gamma) = \mathbb{P}(P_s(\theta) > \gamma),$$

$$P_s(\theta) = \mathbb{P}(\text{SINR} > \theta | \Phi).$$

Introduction

UAV communication

- Mobility and flexibility.
- Establishing line-of-sight (LoS) link to users.
- Channel fading: Nakagami-m fading.

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (System model)

- TBSs is modeled by a PPP.
- Matern cluster process (MCP): user cluster centers is modeled by a PPP, and UAVs are deployed at cluster centers.
- PPP users: UAVs and users are modeled by two independent PPPs.

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (System model)

- The received power of the typical user, when associates with a UAV,

$$P_u = \begin{cases} p_{u,l} = \eta_l \rho_u G_l R_u^{-\alpha_l}, & \text{in the case of LoS,} \\ p_{u,n} = \eta_n \rho_u G_n R_u^{-\alpha_n}, & \text{in the case of NLoS,} \end{cases}$$

in which $G_{\{.\}}$ is the channel fading, R_u is the distance, $\alpha_{\{.\}}$ is the path loss, $\eta_{\{.\}}$ is the mean additional loss and ρ_u is the transmit power of UAVs.

- When associates with a TBS,

$$p_t = \rho_t H R_t^{-\alpha_t}.$$

in which H is the channel fading, R_t is the distance, $\alpha_{\{.\}}$ is the path loss, and ρ_t is the transmit power of TBSs.

LoS channel probability is given by:

$$P_l(r) = \frac{1}{1 + e_1 \exp(-e_2(\frac{180}{\pi} \arctan(\frac{h}{r}) - e_1))}.$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (System model)

- Conditional success probability:

$$P_s(\theta) = \mathbb{P}(\text{SINR} > \theta \mid \Phi_t, \Phi_{u,\{1,2\}}, \Phi_{\text{user}}).$$

- SINR meta distribution:

$$\bar{F}_{P_s}(\theta, \gamma) = \mathbb{P}(P_s(\theta) > \gamma).$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- SINR meta distribution: exact expression

$$\bar{F}_{P_s}(\theta, \gamma) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\Im(\exp(-jt \log \gamma) M_{jt}(\theta))}{t} dt,$$

where $M_{jt}(\theta)$ is the jt -th moment of the conditional success probability $P_s(\theta)$, j is the imaginary unit. $M_{jt}(\theta)$ is computed by replacing the b in $M_b(\theta)$ that we derived in previous sections, and \Im is the imaginary part of a complex number.

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- SINR meta distribution: beta approximation

$$\bar{F}'_{P_s}(\theta, \gamma) \approx 1 - I_\gamma \left(\frac{M_1(\theta)(M_1(\theta) - M_2(\theta))}{M_2(\theta) - M_1^2(\theta)}, \frac{(M_1(\theta) - M_2(\theta))(1 - M_1(\theta))}{M_2(\theta) - M_1^2(\theta)} \right),$$

$$I_x(a, b) = \frac{\int_0^x t^{a-1} (1-t)^{b-1} dt}{B(a, b)},$$

$$B(a, b) = \int_0^1 t^{a-1} (1-t)^{b-1} dt.$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- SINR meta distribution: dominant interferer-based approximation:

$$\bar{F}'_1(\theta, \gamma) \approx \int_0^{\infty} F_{R_0|R_1}(K_1(r, \theta, \gamma)) f_{R_1}(r) dr,$$

$$K_1(r, \theta, \gamma) = \left(-\frac{1}{\theta r^{-\alpha}} + \frac{1}{s(r)} W\left(0, \frac{s(r) \exp(s(r) \theta^{-1} r^{\alpha})}{\gamma \theta r^{-\alpha}}\right) \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}},$$

$$s(r) = \frac{\theta}{p_t} (p_t G(r) + \sigma^2), \quad G(r) = \frac{2\pi\lambda}{\alpha - 2} r^{2-\alpha}.$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- b -th moment of conditional success probability:

$$M_b(\theta) = \mathbb{E}[P_s^b(\theta)].$$

- Conditional success probability:

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_s(\theta) &= \mathbb{P}(\text{SINR} > \theta | \Phi_t, \Phi_{u,1}, \Phi_{\text{user}}) = \mathbb{P}\left(\frac{\max(p_u, p_t)}{I + \sigma^2} > \theta | \Phi_t, \Phi_{u,1}, \Phi_{\text{user}}\right) \\
 &= \mathbb{1}(\text{LoS})\mathbb{1}(R_t > d_{lt}(R_u))\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_{u,l}}{I_{u,l} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) + \mathbb{1}(\text{NLoS})\mathbb{1}(R_t > d_{nt}(R_u))\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_{u,n}}{I_{u,n} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) \\
 &\quad + \mathbb{1}(\text{LoS})\mathbb{1}(R_t < d_{lt}(R_u))\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_t}{I_{t,l} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) + \mathbb{1}(\text{NLoS})\mathbb{1}(R_t < d_{nt}(R_u))\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_t}{I_{t,n} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) \\
 &= P_{s,l}(\theta) + P_{s,n}(\theta) + P_{s,tl}(\theta) + P_{s,tn}(\theta), \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (Numerical results)

(a) $\gamma = 0.3$.

(b) $\gamma = 0.9$.

Fig. 4. The simulation and beta approximation results of the SINR meta distribution in the case that users are spatially-clustered, under different values of γ . Markers are for simulation and solid/dashed lines are for analysis.

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (Numerical results)

(a) Highrise urban areas ($e_1 = 27, e_2 = 0.08$), $\gamma = 0.9$.

(b) Highrise urban areas ($e_1 = 27, e_2 = 0.08$), $\theta = 1$.

Fig. 8. The simulation and beta approximation results of the SINR meta distributions of PPP users, in the case of highrise urban areas. Markers are for simulation and solid/dashed lines are for analysis.

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (Numerical results)

- We show that optimal altitudes exist to maximize the system reliability and the optimal altitudes increase with the decrease of the LoS probabilities.
- We show that optimal densities exist to maximize the system reliability. Optimal densities increase with the decrease of the LoS probability and the ratios of optimal UAV density to TBS density are \$0.4\$, \$2.5\$ and \$5\$ for suburban, urban and dense urban areas.

Conclusion

- **For the downlink transmission, when the locations of users exhibit a certain degree of clustering, deploying UAVs can highly improve communication reliability, especially at low values of the SINR threshold.** In the case of highrise urban areas, deploying a UAV for each cluster seems to only slightly improve the reliability.
- Besides, we showed that **the system does not always benefit from increasing LoS probabilities:** on the one side, it improves the signal. On the other side, it increases the interference and, therefore, decreases the probability of establishing extremely reliable channels (which can achieve a very high SINR, as mentioned above).
- For the urban area, the operators need to decrease UAVs' altitude and density to maintain a reliable network.

Thank you!

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- Conditional success probability:

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_{u,l}}{I_{u,l} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) = \left(G_l > \frac{\theta}{\eta_l \rho_u} R_u^{\alpha_l} (I_{u,l} + \sigma^2)\right) \stackrel{(a)}{=} \frac{\Gamma_u(m_l, m_l g_l(R_u)(I_{u,l} + \sigma^2))}{\Gamma(m_l)}$$

$$\stackrel{(b)}{\leq} 1 - (1 - \exp(-s_l(R_u)(I_{u,l} + \sigma^2)))^{m_l}$$

$$\stackrel{(c)}{=} \sum_{k_l=1}^{m_l} (-1)^{k_l+1} \exp(-k_l s_l(R_u)(I_{u,l} + \sigma^2)),$$

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_{u,n}}{I_{u,n} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) = \frac{\Gamma_u(m_n, m_n g_n(R_u)(I_{u,n} + \sigma^2))}{\Gamma(m_n)}$$

$$\leq \sum_{k_n=1}^{m_n} (-1)^{k_n+1} \exp(-k_n s_n(R_u)(I_{u,n} + \sigma^2)),$$

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{p_t}{I_{\{tl,tn\}} + \sigma^2} > \theta\right) = \mathbb{P}\left(h_0 > \frac{\theta}{\rho_t} R_t^{\alpha_t} (I_{\{tl,tn\}} + \sigma^2)\right) = \exp(-s_t(R_t)(I_{\{tl,tn\}} + \sigma^2)),$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- b-th moments:

Theorem 1 (*b*-th Moments). *The b-th moment of the conditional success probability is given by*

$$M_b(\theta) = M_{b,l}(\theta) + M_{b,n}(\theta) + M_{b,tl}(\theta) + M_{b,tn}(\theta), \quad (17)$$

in which

$$M_{b,l}(\theta) \approx \sum_{k_1=1}^{m_l} \sum_{k_2=1}^{m_l} \cdots \sum_{k_b=1}^{m_l} \binom{m_l}{k_1} \binom{m_l}{k_2} \cdots \binom{m_l}{k_b} (-1)^{\sum_{i=1}^b k_i + b} \int_h^{\sqrt{r_c^2 + h^2}} P_l(\sqrt{x^2 - h^2}) \\ \times \mathcal{A}_{\text{LoS},1}(x) \mathcal{L}_{ul}(s_2(l, k_1, x), s_2(l, k_2, x), \cdots, s_2(l, k_b, x), x) \frac{2x}{r_c^2} dx, \quad (18)$$

$$M_{b,n}(\theta) \approx \sum_{k_1=1}^{m_n} \sum_{k_2=1}^{m_n} \cdots \sum_{k_b=1}^{m_n} \binom{m_n}{k_1} \binom{m_n}{k_2} \cdots \binom{m_n}{k_b} (-1)^{\sum_{i=1}^b k_i + b} \int_h^{\sqrt{r_c^2 + h^2}} P_n(\sqrt{x^2 - h^2}) \\ \times \mathcal{A}_{\text{NLoS},1}(x) \mathcal{L}_{un}(s_2(n, k_1, x), s_2(n, k_2, x), \cdots, s_2(n, k_b, x), x) \frac{2x}{r_c^2} dx, \quad (19)$$

$$M_{b,tl}(\theta) \approx \int_h^{\sqrt{r_c^2 + h^2}} \int_0^{d_{lt}(y)} P_l(\sqrt{y^2 - h^2}) \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{tl}(b, y) \frac{2y}{r_c^2} dy, \quad (20)$$

$$M_{b,tn}(\theta) \approx \int_h^{\sqrt{r_c^2 + h^2}} \int_0^{d_{nt}(y)} P_n(\sqrt{y^2 - h^2}) \tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{tn}(b, y) \frac{2y}{r_c^2} dy, \quad (21)$$

SINR Meta Distribution of UAV networks

Downlink performance (analysis)

- b-th moments:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{L}_{uj}(s_2(j, k_1, x), s_2(j, k_2, x), \dots, s_2(j, k_b, x), x) \\
 &= \exp\left(-2\pi\lambda_t \int_{d_{jt}(x)}^{\infty} \left[1 - \prod_{i=1}^b f_1(s_2(j, k_i, x), z, \alpha_t)\right] z dz\right) \\
 & \times \prod_{e \in \{l, n\}} \exp\left(-2\pi\lambda_u \int_h^{\infty} \left[1 - \prod_{i=1}^b f_2(m_e, s_2(j, k_i, x), \eta_e, z, \alpha_e)\right] z P_e(\sqrt{z^2 - h^2}) dz\right) \\
 & \times \exp\left(-\sum_{i=1}^b s_2(j, i, x) \sigma^2\right), \quad j \in \{l, n\}, \tag{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{\mathcal{L}}_{tj}(b, x) = \int_0^{d_{jt}(x)} f_{R_t}(r) f_2^b(m_j, s_t(r), \eta_j, r, \alpha_j) \mathcal{L}(b, s_t(r)) \mathcal{L}_t(b, s_t(r), r) dr, \quad j \in \{l, n\}, \tag{23}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_t(b, s, r) = \exp\left(-2\pi\lambda_t \int_r^{\infty} \left[1 - f_1^b(s, z, \alpha_t)\right] z dz\right), \tag{24}$$

$$\mathcal{L}(b, s) = \prod_{e \in \{l, n\}} \exp\left(-2\pi\lambda_{u,1} \int_0^{\infty} \left[1 - f_2^b(m_e, s, \eta_e, z, \alpha_e)\right] \sqrt{z^2 + h^2} P_e(z) dz\right) \exp(-bs\sigma^2).$$